

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF DAMAGED SEEDS ON THE ABRASION OF WORKING SURFACES

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Abstract.

The article analyzes the effect of cotton seed on friction on working surfaces after the ginning process in cotton ginning enterprises. That is, after the process of cleaning and sorting seeds, the level of their damage in different varieties was studied. According to the results of the analysis, it was emphasized that it is necessary to produce devices that work with high reliability while reducing the negative impact of seed sorting devices on seed quality.

Keywords.

Cotton, seed, fiber, sorter, friction, stringiness, pressure, mass, damage, productivity.

Introduction. After the ginning process at the cotton ginning plant, cotton seeds are sent to processes such as cleaning from various impurities, linting, delinting. The seeds intended for planting are sent to the sorting process.

Both a single seed and a mass of seeds have a number of properties that allow determining the effect of transportation, storage technology on their processing, and it is called technological properties. The main part of these properties is physico-mechanical, significantly biological, determined by the nature of the material and affects the technological process in different amounts. Based on these, they can be conventionally divided into physical-mechanical, mechanical-technological and technological parts.

In this case, the physico-mechanical properties of seed and seed mass differ from each other in many cases. In addition, in contrast to scientific and research centers, conventional measurement quantities are still used in cotton ginning enterprises.

Main part. Depending on the hairiness of the seeds after germination, they have several different values that characterize their frictional properties.

The main quantities representing the frictional property are the coefficients of friction at rest and sliding. Also included in this property is releasability, the opposite of which is adhesion, which is determined by adhesive strength.

Theoreticians, designers, manufacturers and other specialists are faced with the seed friction coefficient in the technological process of processing cotton seeds, in the design of seed processing machines and their parts, as well as in the introduction of developments into production. The hairiness of the seeds being processed gives them different friction properties.

When determining the coefficient of friction of the seeds, it was believed that this coefficient decreases by increasing the pressure on the seeds, ensuring the cleanliness of the surface and reducing the humidity. Depending on the slip, an increase in speed up to 0.4-0.8 m/s leads to an increase in the coefficient of friction.

This coefficient becomes less important at low hairiness and low pressure. When the speed is increased again, the coefficient of friction decreases.

The coefficient of friction in sliding is found by the following formula known from theoretical mechanics for linear models:

$$\mu_0 = \operatorname{tg} \alpha - \frac{g_H}{g \cdot \cos \alpha}$$

where α is the slope of the plane to the horizon; g_H - acceleration of the sample along the plane; g - acceleration of gravity.

Taking the sample acceleration as constant ($a = \text{const}$), we find it using the following formula:

$$a = \frac{2S}{t^2}$$

where S is the path of the sample in time t .

In a seed sorter with an inclined surface, the frictional force in vibration is generated by the deformation of the fibrous sheath during the contact of the seed with the surface.

The following conditions must be met for the vibration of cotton seeds:

$$N + G = 0 \text{ or } G \cos \alpha - cy_1 = 0;$$

$$G \sin \alpha - F = -P; N = G \cos \alpha; P \cdot r = Nk$$

Where G is seed weight; N - normal reaction of the support plane; r - seed radius; f_0 is the sliding friction coefficient;

$$\kappa - k/r = -\operatorname{tg} \alpha + f_0 \text{ friction coefficient of vibration found by the formula.}$$

The area of contact with the surface also increases with the increase of fiber of the seeds. Therefore, seeds with a high fiber level in most cases slide, movement by vibration occurs at large slope angles. According to the results of the conducted

studies, the coefficient of vibration friction of seeds with 8, 10, 13% fiber content is 0.91; 1.21; It is equal to 2.1.

Table 1

Friction coefficient of S-6524 cotton seed

Material type	Cotton seed fiber,%					
	8,1		10,01		13,2	
	K ₀	K _c	K ₀	K _c	K ₀	K _c
Steel	0,5890	0,5850	0,5890	0,5728	0,577	0,672
The rubber side of the conveyor belt	0,6008	0,6016	0,6003	0,5800	0,589	0,600
The fabric side of the conveyor belt	0,7002		0,8339		0,9656	

The amount of fiber left in the seed is called the amount of fiber left in 200 seeds during ginning of cotton [4]. The fiber residue of seeds after germinating [5] is a necessary indicator that ensures the normal passage of the germinating process. However, in research studies, it was found that 3-5% of the seeds from the ginning process contain fibers suitable for spinning [6-7]. Therefore, it is desirable to isolate these seeds in the maximum condition.

Result. The degree of their damage also has a significant impact on the process of sorting seeds. Studies on seed damage during ginning and linting revealed the following. For example, S-6524 1 grade 50 g. For cotton seeds, 2-3%, 9-22% in the middle, 3-6% in the stem are damaged, while for S-6530 II seeds, this value is 1-3% in the third, 8-19% in the middle, 2-5% in the stem. it is. This 'distribution' of hull damage can also be described in terms of natural physical properties of cotton seeds.

Conclusion. Based on the above, it can be noted that in the current conditions, it is necessary to produce devices that work with high reliability while reducing the negative impact of the devices that work in the process of seed sorting.

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